

**FROM MONKEYS TO LARGE LANGUAGE MODELS:
REVISITING NARUTO v. SLATER IN THE ERA OF GENERATIVE AI –
AN ESSAY**

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ABSTRACT - The landmark decision in *Naruto v. Slater*, popularly known as the “Monkey Selfie Case,” is often remembered for answering a peculiar question: can an animal own copyright? Yet, the case raises a far more significant issue that remains unresolved today: the extent to which non-human authorship can be recognized, especially with the rise of generative Artificial Intelligence.

The essay starts with a thorough analysis of the *Naruto* case. Building on 4 principles that emerge from the judgment, the essay then considers how similar questions arise in the context of AI-generated works, where the relationship between human contribution and creative output is often unclear. Rather than merely examining existing authorities, the essay develops its own observations from the reasoning in *Naruto* and applies them to contemporary disputes involving generative AI. Combined with an analysis of judicial decisions and statutory provisions, it considers whether traditional copyright law remains capable of addressing works created with modern technology, i.e., Artificial Intelligence.

It further argues that the future of copyright law may ultimately depend on identifying the degree of human creativity embedded within a work rather than merely identifying who or what produced it.

ANALYZING NARUTO v. SLATER

INTRODUCTION

It must be noted that India does not yet have strong judicial precedent on non-human authorship in copyright law. Therefore, scholars often rely on precedents in countries with stronger IP protection like the US for guidance, one such case being discussed below.

The landmark “Gorilla Selfie case,” i.e, *Naruto v David Slater*, answered the easy question: can an animal own a copyright? However, a more central question that decides copyrights in the present era still remains untouched: what human contribution is sufficient to constitute authorship? Revisiting *Naruto* in the age of AI-generated works becomes especially significant because, unlike the question with David Slater, AI cannot easily be regarded as an “author” within traditional legal frameworks. The essay starts with the facts of the case to get a contextual understanding of what is being analyzed in this essay.

FACTS

Naruto, a seven-year-old crested macaque living in an Indonesian reserve, became the centre of an unusual copyright dispute in 2011. Wildlife photographer David Slater had put his camera on a tripod with a wide-angle lens, predictive autofocus, motor drive, and a flash gun to maximize the chance of a facial close-up of the macaque. *Naruto* took several photographs using Slater’s unattended camera. Slater later published these photographs, popularly known as the “Monkey Selfies,” in a book through Wildlife Personalities Ltd, and Blurb Inc. He claimed copyright ownership over them, despite acknowledging in the book itself that the monkey had taken the pictures using phrases such as “Sulawesi crested black macaque smiles at itself while pressing the shutter button on a camera” and describing *Naruto* as ““posing to take its own photograph, unworried by its own reflection, smiling. Surely a sign of self-awareness?”

In 2015 PETA and Dr. Antje Engelhardt filed a complaint for copyright infringement against Slater, Wildlife, and Blurb, as Next Friends on behalf of *Naruto* before the United States District Court for the Northern District of California. The complaint alleges that Dr. Engelhardt has studied the crested macaques in Sulawesi, Indonesia for over a decade and has known, monitored, and studied *Naruto* since his birth. PETA stated that it is “the largest animal rights organization in the world” and “has championed establishing the rights and legal protections available to animals beyond their utility to human beings...” Slater, Wildlife, and Blurb filed

motions to dismiss on the grounds that there was no sufficient standing for the complaint under Article III or statutory standing under the Copyright Act.

ISSUE –

1. Whether Naruto, an animal, had standing to sue under Article III of the United States Constitution and has statutory standing under the United States Copyright Act?
2. Whether PETA could validly act as Naruto’s “next friend” in bringing the lawsuit?
3. Whether animals can own copyrights or sue for copyright infringement?

RULE

Article III of the United States Constitution limits the jurisdiction of federal courts to actual “cases” and “controversies.” Only a party with the legal capacity to sue may invoke the jurisdiction of a federal court.

Laws relating to Copyright start from the United States Copyright Act, 17 U.S.C. § 101 et seq. Section 102(a)¹ extends copyright protection to “original works of authorship fixed in any tangible medium of expression.” Copyright ownership initially vests in the author of the work under Section 201(a)², while Section 501(b)³ provides that only the “legal or beneficial owner of an exclusive right under a copyright” is entitled to sue for infringement. The Act does not expressly grant animals the right to sue for copyright infringement. The Copyright Act does not define the term “author.” Therefore, one has to derive the meaning of authorship from the statutory framework as a whole. U.S.C §201, §203, and §304⁴, refer to an author's “children,” “grandchildren,” “widow,” and “widower” in relation to copyright ownership, indicating that copyright ownership under the Act is contemplated in relation to human authors.

The doctrine of “next friend” was established in the case of Whitmore⁵, wherein, a person seeking to litigate on behalf of another must establish: (i) an adequate explanation, such as incapacity or disability, showing why the real party in interest cannot appear; and (ii) a significant relationship with the interests of the real party in interest. Federal Rule of Civil Procedure 17(c) permits a representative, guardian, or next friend to sue on behalf of a minor or an incompetent person who lacks a duly appointed representative⁶. 17 U.S.C. § 505 states

¹ 17 U.S.C. § 102(a).

² 17 U.S.C. § 201(a)

³ 17 U.S.C. § 501(b)

⁴ 17 U.S.C. §§ 101, 201, 203, 304

⁵ Whitmore v. Arkansas, 495 U.S. 149 (1990).

⁶ Fed. R. Civ. P. 17(c)

that in any civil action under this title, the court in its discretion may allow the recovery of full costs by or against any party other than the United States or an officer thereof.

ANALYSIS

COURT'S REASONING AND JUDGEMENT

CONSTITUTIONAL STANDING

The majority held that Naruto had Article III standing. In a prior landmark judgement *Cetacean Community v. Bush*⁷, the Ninth Circuit observed that “*it is possible for animals, like humans, to demonstrate the kind of case or controversy required to establish Article III standing*”. Although the majority in the present case believed *Cetacean* was incorrectly decided, it is binding circuit precedent until and unless overruled by an en banc panel or the Supreme Court. Therefore, the court said that Article III did not automatically exclude animals from federal court, and that the complaint alleged a concrete economic injury because Naruto was claimed to be the author and owner of the photographs.

NEXT FRIEND STANDING

To establish next-friend standing, the putative next friend must show: (1) that the petitioner is unable to litigate his own cause due to mental incapacity, lack of access to court, or other similar disability; and (2) the next friend has some significant relationship with, and is truly dedicated to the best interests of, the petitioner⁸.” The judges observed that with respect to the second requirement, PETA does not claim to have a relationship with Naruto that is any more significant than its relationship with any other animal. Thus, PETA cannot sue as Naruto’s next friend. While Congress has authorized next friend lawsuits for habeas petitioners and for minors or incompetent persons⁹, there is no such authorization for lawsuits brought on behalf of animals.

STANDING UNDER THE COPYRIGHT ACT: COULD NARUTO CLAIM COPYRIGHT INFRINGEMENT?

⁷ *Cetacean Cmty. v. Bush*, 386 F.3d 1169, 1179 (9th Cir. 2004)

⁸ *Coalition of Clergy v. Bush*, 310 F.3d 1153, 1159–60 (9th Cir. 2002)

⁹ *Whitmore v. Arkansas*, 495 U.S. 149 (1990).

Now, we come to the main crux of the analysis. While the majority did hold that Naruto had constitutional standing, it must not be confused with statutory standing under the Copyright Act. PETA argued that the Copyright Act contemplates statutory standing for animals because it permits such standing for corporations and unincorporated associations without express authorization. However, *Cetacean*¹⁰ held that, "*If Congress and the President intended to take the extraordinary step of authorizing animals as well as people and legal entities to sue, they could, and should, have said so plainly.*" The Copyright Act expressly recognizes corporations and other legal entities as authors in the context of works made for hire¹¹ under 17 U.S.C. § 201(b), but it contains no comparable provision for animals. Moreover, corporations and unincorporated associations are formed and owned by humans; they are not formed or owned by animals. Therefore, in terms of copyright infringement, the two are not comparable, and Naruto was held not to have statutory standing under the Copyright Act. The court noted that under § 501(b), only a legal or beneficial owner of an exclusive copyright interest may sue¹². Because Naruto could not qualify as a statutory author under the Copyright Act's framework, he could not claim ownership rights capable of enforcement.

The court relied on a judicial precedent to further reason this decision, which states that statutory words must be read in context and in light of the overall statutory scheme¹³. Therefore, the court used the structure of the Copyright Act to support its reasoning. Provisions such as 17 U.S.C. §§ 101, 201, 203, and 304, deal with copyright definitions, ownership, and the inheritance and termination of authors' rights. They explicitly refer to an author's "children," "grandchildren," "widow," and "widower." The court reasoned that these terms show the statute is built around human authorship and inheritance, not animal authorship.

Finally, the U.S. Copyright Office entered the fray, writing that it would not award human copyright to "photographs and artwork created by animals or by machines without human intervention"¹⁴ thus delivering an affirmative stance on the same.

¹⁰ *Cetacean Cmty. v. Bush*, 386 F.3d 1169, 1179 (9th Cir. 2004)

¹¹ 17 U.S.C. § 201(b)

¹² 17 U.S.C. § 501(b)

¹³ *Davis v. Michigan Department of Treasury* 489 US 803 (1989)

¹⁴ Jacob Axelrad, "U.S. Government: Monkey Selfies Ineligible for Copyright," *Christian Science Monitor*, August 22, 2014, <https://www.csmonitor.com/Technology/Tech-Culture/2014/0822/US-government-Monkey-selfies-ineligible-for-copyright>.

The final judgment was that the Ninth Circuit affirmed the dismissal of the lawsuit and held that Naruto lacked statutory standing under the Copyright Act to sue for copyright infringement. It also granted appellees' request for appellate attorneys' fees under 17 U.S.C. § 505.

IMPLICATION OF THE JUDGEMENT

Although the Ninth Circuit ultimately dismissed the case on statutory standing grounds, the dispute raises broader questions regarding the level of human contribution required for copyright ownership. The court did not hold that the Monkey Selfies were in the public domain, nor did it determine who owned the copyright in the photographs. But it did provide insight into circumstances in which a human creator may retain copyright despite the involvement of a non-human actor. Copyright ownership may be more readily established where the human contributes substantial creative input, such as:

1. The "Setup" Argument: Designing and configuring specific equipment to achieve a specific artistic effect.
2. The "Direction" Rule: The amount of creative control by the author to achieve a specific expression.
3. The "Selection" Process: selecting and curating specific images from numerous images that reflects their personal artistic vision.
4. The "Assistant" Theory: treating the non-human actor as a tool or assistant through which the human's creative vision is expressed.

Viewed through this lens, the outcome may have been different had David Slater demonstrated a greater degree of creative control over the final images. A possible explanation for the controversy surrounding ownership is that Slater repeatedly acknowledged that the macaque itself pressed the shutter button and generated the specific expression captured in the photographs, which was the "creative spark" needed to establish ownership over the copyright.

THE DEBATE OVER COPYRIGHT AND AI

An anthropomorphic vision of AI is deeply embedded in the term itself because “intelligence” is commonly considered to be specifically human¹⁵. This term lacks, however, a standardized definition within the scientific community¹⁶. For the purpose of this analysis, we can use a generic definition of AI as stated below:-

High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (AI HLEG) of the European Commission (EC) defines AI as ‘systems that display intelligent behaviour by analyzing their environment and taking actions with some degree of autonomy to achieve specific goals.’¹⁷

Drawing a parallel to the above-mentioned case, Artificial Intelligence, just like the black-crested macaque Naruto, is undoubtedly not a “human” in the sense explained above nor can it be considered a subset of a company, association or organization. This principle is not limited to copyright alone. In patent law, the Supreme Court in *Novartis AG v. Union of India*¹⁸ read the terms "created or invented" as requiring human intervention, a logic that traces back to Lord Kenyon's observation in *Hornblower v. Boulton*¹⁹ that a patent protects something made by the hands of man. But since AI is mainly disruptive in the domain of creative authorship and not invention, the burning questions of today are the intersection between generative AI and copyright. Authorship has been inextricably linked to human creation for generations.

Therefore, a central question arises: what degree of human contribution is required before a work can be said to possess a legally recognizable author who can hold copyright? Unlike Naruto, whose inability to hold copyright stemmed from his status as an animal, modern AI systems pose a different challenge. The issue is no longer whether a non-human entity can own copyright, but whether a work generated substantially by a non-human entity can satisfy the requirement of human authorship in the first place.

The four theories of *Setup, Direction, Selection, and Assistant* above were shaped around a monkey and a camera. But they matter far more today, because the same question is now being asked about generative AI tools like ChatGPT, Claude, Gemini, DALL-E, etc. The non-human

¹⁵ Wang, Pei, “On Defining Artificial Intelligence”, *Journal of Artificial General Intelligence*, vol. 10, n o 2, 2019, p. 1-37

¹⁶ Scherer, Matthew U., “Regulating Artificial Intelligence Systems : Risks, Challenges, Competencies, and Strategies”, *Harvard Journal of Law & Technology*, vol. 29, no 2, 2016

¹⁷ Haroon Sheikh et al., *Mission AI the New System Technology* (Springer 2023)

¹⁸ *Novartis AG v. Union of India*, (2013) 6 SCC 1, 154, para 71 : (2013) 3 SCC (Civ) 227

¹⁹ *Hornblower v. Boulton* [(1799) 8 TR 95 : 101 ER 1285.]

actor has changed. The legal problem has not. In Naruto's case, the human sets up the camera, the monkey then presses the button, and a photo, which is the subject of copyright, is created. Similarly, in the case of Generative AI, the human writes and sends a prompt, based on which the AI generates an output, and the work, which is the subject of copyright, is created. But the latter gets a bit more complex. With Naruto, the creative contribution question was binary, but contrasting that with AI, human contribution exists on a spectrum. A one-word prompt ("picturesque sunset") involves almost no human creativity, whereas a 200-word detailed prompt specifying composition, lighting, style, and mood involves substantial creative direction. The law currently has no framework for this spectrum.

APPLYING THE FOUR THEORIES TO AI

The Setup Theory asks whether configuring an AI system counts as creative authorship. An AI user selects a model, adjusts its parameters, and sometimes fine-tunes it on specific datasets. This is arguably no different from choosing which brand of camera to buy and adjusting its settings before a shoot. It is a precondition for creation, not creation itself. On its own, this is unlikely to be sufficient for authorship.

The Direction Theory is the main point of contention for AI authorship. A detailed prompt that specifies style, composition, tone, and content reflects something closer to genuine creative direction. The Copyright Office's reasoning in *Zarya of the Dawn* (which is explained below) implicitly supports this as well because the human-written text in that case was protected precisely because it reflected human creative choices. The problem is that no court has drawn the line between a creative prompt and a functional instruction. Telling an AI to produce a blue landscape painting in the style of Monet may reflect genuine artistic direction. Typing "generate an image" does not.

The Selection Theory may be the most legally defensible basis available right now. When a human generates dozens of photographs, for example, and selects, edits, and arranges specific results into a final work, that "act of curating" has attracted copyright protection. Editors and anthologists have similarly received protection for selection and arrangement. There is no principled reason why the same logic should not apply to someone curating AI outputs, provided the selection reflects genuine creative judgment.

The Assistant Theory treats AI as a sophisticated tool, no different from Photoshop. The human's creative vision is the authorship, and the AI merely executes it. This works cleanly when the AI does exactly what it is told. It becomes harder to sustain when the AI produces

outputs that genuinely surprise even its own creators. When researchers at Google DeepMind tested their AlphaGo system, it made moves in the game of Go that its own programmers described as unexpected²⁰. Is a tool that makes independent creative decisions still just a tool?

THE LEGAL POSITION SO FAR

In *Thaler v. Perlmutter*²¹, Stephen Thaler tried to register a painting generated entirely by his AI system DABUS, listing the AI as author. The Copyright Office refused. The court upheld the refusal, holding that human authorship is the most basic requirement under the Copyright Act. The court relied on the same statutory reasoning the Ninth Circuit used in *Naruto*. The Copyright Act's structure assumes a human author throughout, and AI is simply not an author in that sense.

Now, we move on to the Copyright Office's 2023 decision in *Zarya of the Dawn*²². Kris Kashtanova used Midjourney to create a graphic novel. The Office granted copyright over the text and the arrangement of images because those reflected human creative choices. It refused protection for the individual AI-generated images. It shows the law is moving toward selective protection based on how much human contribution exists in each element. Only that portion of the work which reflects human creative-decision making will be protected.

*Burrow-Giles Lithographic Co. v. Sarony*²³ is an old case that is revisited by scholars in such debates. The Supreme Court held that a photograph could attract copyright if the photographer made deliberate creative choices about lighting, positioning, and expression. That reasoning is exactly what Slater tried and failed to establish in *Naruto*. It is also the strongest doctrinal basis for protecting AI-assisted works today, provided the human behind the prompt can demonstrate genuine creative direction and control.

*Feist Publications v. Rural Telephone*²⁴ established that for a work to attract copyright protection, it must result from independent creation and contain at least a minimal creative spark. The Supreme Court was clear that purely mechanical or automated processes cannot produce this spark because there is no human mind making creative choices behind the output. When applied to a generative AI system, it does not independently create anything. It produces

²⁰ Google DeepMind, AlphaGo, <https://deepmind.google/research/alphago/> (last visited May 31, 2026).

²¹ *Thaler v. Perlmutter*, 22-CV-384-1564-BAH (2023)

²² U.S. Copyright Office, Re: *Zarya of the Dawn* (Registration No. VAu001480196) (Feb. 21, 2023), <https://www.copyright.gov/docs/zarya-of-the-dawn.pdf>

²³ *Burrow-Giles Lithographic Co. v. Sarony* 111 U.S. 53 (1884)

²⁴ *Feist Publications, Inc. v. Rural Telephone Service Co.*, 499 U.S. 340

outputs by identifying statistical patterns across billions of data points it was trained on²⁵. The result may look creative, but the process behind it is closer to sophisticated pattern-matching than genuine independent creation, which isn't enough to meet the minimal creative spark test to claim copyright.

The US principle of 'modicum of creativity' has been considered and laid down according to Indian circumstances in *Eastern Book Company v. D.B Modak*²⁶ which has become increasingly relevant in the context of Generative AI. The word 'original' does not necessarily mean that the work must be the expression of original or inventive thought. With respect to derivative work, originality is a matter of degree depending on the amount of skill, judgment or labour that has been involved in making the compilation. This standard becomes harder to apply cleanly when the work is generated by AI. Instead of the computer making selections within a human-built framework like before, the AI is now, based on the training it has received, independently producing the creative output itself. If we assume the skill and judgement thereby belong to the AI now and not the human, this standard that has governed copyright for ages cannot be applied to generative AI.

in India, courts have not yet conclusively addressed AI authorship. However, Section 2(d)(vi) of the Indian Copyright Act says the author of a computer-generated work is "the person who causes the work to be created." This appears more flexible than the American position because it attributes authorship of computer-generated works to the person causing the work to be created. India implicitly anticipated non-human generation and assigned authorship to the human facilitator. Under Indian law, an AI-generated work would likely be owned by whoever caused its creation. That could be the prompter, the developer, or even the company deploying the model. The problem is that "causes the work to be created" is undefined. Does writing a prompt cause the creation? Does training the model? Does deploying it commercially?

In the author's opinion, the provision does not take into consideration any computer machine that is intelligent to act as humans. It only considers those computers that are operated by human agency or have some amount of human interaction²⁷. Furthermore, under Chapter V of the Indian Copyright Act, in §22, the act talks about the term of the copyright in published literary, dramatic, musical and artistic works. The term of any work published within the "lifetime" of

²⁵ J. Horst., *A Native Intelligence Metric for Artificial Systems*, The NAT'1 Inst. STANDARDS & Tech., (August 1, 2002) https://tsapps.nist.gov/publication/get_pdf.cfm?pub_id=824478

²⁶ *Eastern Book Company v. D.B Modak* (2008) 1 SCC

²⁷ Who Owns Computer Generated Works, Learn and Digest Blog (June, 2014), <http://learndigest.blogspot.com/2014/06/who-owns-computer-generated-works.html>

the author until sixty years from the beginning of the calendar year following the year in which the author “dies.” The intention of the legislators was therefore only to include mortal beings as subjects of copyright law. So, under current law, the author must be a living being or at least a corporation comprising living beings.²⁸

In November 2025, the Regional Court of Munich delivered a landmark copyright ruling in *GEMA v. OpenAI*²⁹. GEMA, Germany's music rights society, alleged that OpenAI had used copyrighted song lyrics to train ChatGPT without obtaining a licence. It also argued that ChatGPT could reproduce substantial portions of those lyrics when prompted. The court agreed and held that AI systems may infringe copyright where they reproduce protected works without authorization. As a result, OpenAI was directed to stop the unauthorized use of the material, disclose information relating to its training data, and pay damages.

Asian News International (ANI) has also filed a copyright infringement lawsuit against OpenAI in the Delhi High Court³⁰, alleging that ChatGPT was trained on ANI's copyrighted news articles, including paywalled content, without permission. It further claims that ChatGPT has reproduced portions of its reports and, on certain occasions, generated inaccurate content attributed to ANI. ANI has sought an injunction restraining the use of its content and has requested the removal of ANI material from OpenAI's training datasets. The matter is presently pending adjudication, and the Court has issued notice to OpenAI.

The Indian Copyright Office, marking the first instance of AI recognition as a co-author, recognized the RAGHAV Artificial Intelligence Painting App as a co-author of a copyright-protected artwork in a landmark 2021 verdict. This development indicates a move toward AI being regarded as the sole author. In China, organizations or non-legal-person entities are recognized as writers, provided they convey intent in the work and assert ownership. Such legal frameworks classify AI as non-natural legal entities, bridging the gap between AI and traditional copyright law.³¹

CONCLUSION

Naruto v. Slater is often remembered as a dispute over whether a monkey could own copyright. However, its enduring significance lies in the broader question it left unanswered: what degree

²⁸ Artificial Intelligence Generated Works Under Copyright Law, 6.2 NLUJ LR (2020) 93

²⁹ *GEMA v. OpenAI*, Case No. 42 O 14139/24

³⁰ *ANI v OpenAI*, CS(COMM) 1028/2024

³¹ *Shenzhen Tencent Computer System Co. Ltd. v. Shanghai Yingxun Technology Co. Ltd.* 0305 Civil First Trial No. 14010

of human contribution is necessary to establish authorship? While the Ninth Circuit ultimately held that Naruto lacked statutory standing under the Copyright Act, it deliberately refrained from deciding who owned the copyright in the Monkey Selfies or whether copyright subsisted in them at all.

The rise of generative artificial intelligence has brought this unresolved question to the forefront of modern copyright law. Unlike Naruto, AI systems are capable of producing text, images, music, and other creative outputs with minimal human intervention. Works developed completely by AI such as ‘The Day a Computer Writes a Novel’ and ‘The Sunlight that Lost the Glass Window, challenge traditional concepts of authorship and copyright ownership. Jurisdictions across the world have adopted differing approaches: the United States continues to insist upon human authorship, China has selectively granted rights in AI-assisted cases, the United Kingdom attributes authorship to the person making the necessary arrangements and the EU Parliament has chosen a middle ground by proposing a legislation that will mandate disclosing all the copyrighted training material used by the AI.³² India, through Section 2(d)(vi) of the Copyright Act, provides a potential framework by recognizing the person who causes a computer-generated work to be created as its author. The theories emerging from Naruto’s analysis, namely Setup, Direction, Selection, and Assistantship, also provide a useful framework for evaluating the degree of human contribution involved in AI-generated works, though they haven’t been formally adopted by Courts.

Ultimately, copyright law is not merely concerned with identifying who or what produced a work, but with determining whether sufficient human intellectual contribution exists to justify legal protection. In that sense, *Naruto v. Slater* may be viewed not simply as a case about animal authorship, but as a defining case regarding non-human authorship with respect to copyright that ultimately is the question today when it comes to AI-generated work. As technology continues to evolve, the future of copyright law will likely depend on balancing innovation with the enduring principle that copyright exists to reward and protect human creativity.

³² Lavanya Jain, *AI and Copyright*, Vidhi Centre for Legal Policy, <https://vidhilegalpolicy.in/blog/ai-and-copyright/> (last visited May 31, 2026).